

OF STUDENTS IN TEACHING AXONOMETRIC PROJECTIONS INCREASING SPATIAL IMAGINATION

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Annotation: In this article, students in the drawing class of higher educational institutions. The role of axonometric projections in improving spatial perception is highlighted.

Key words: Axonometric projection, drawing, spatial perception, image, students, simple, complex, model, orthogonal.

Expanding students' spatial imagination drawing geometry and It is very important in drawing subjects, it makes students creative is one of the factors guiding research. "Reading a drawing means studying a drawing of an object the process by which the spatial image is formed is understood".

Indeed it is, as we have seen in the drawing the height, length and width of the thing and its elements, components and after studying its conditional signs, we embody the thing before our eyes, i.e let's read the drawing. So reading the drawing is done based on its images, knowing and understanding its external and internal structures as a whole it is understood to imagine an image, to know its dimensions, methods of processing.

It can be seen from these that spatial perception is the most important in reading a drawing is an indicator, therefore, if the spatial imagination of students is low, they draw they have difficulty in reading and their interest in drawing decreases. That's why For us, teachers of drawing subjects, we pay all attention to the spatial development of students mobilize all our energy and methodical speech to increase the imagination we will need to do. Only then will we produce the future of young people conditions or educational process.

This is the analysis of topics related to my research work in the main literature show that reading the drawings, that is, imagine the results depicted in the drawing as it is increased in the following order:

- 1). determine the shape of its external surfaces by dividing into figures;
- 2) Using cuts and clippings in the drawing, its interior understand and understand their structures;
- 3) After analyzing and studying the constituent parts of the thing, its whole restoration-imagination of a holistic image in space;
- 4) For example, ($\emptyset$), (R), ($\square$) and ($\triangleright$) from the conventional symbols given in the

drawing addition about some surfaces and surfaces of things using symbols to have an imagination.

In the analyzed literature on the methods of spatial visualization it's just about training methods. To training methods includes the following types.

1. From the drawing of simple, medium, complex and extremely complex objects using them to make a clear image based on simple to complex compare them with their drawings;
 2. Projections corresponding to clear images from the bank of projections finding and its opposite, i.e. what corresponds to the given appearances find the correct image.
 3. Making a drawing of the thing according to the original or obvious view;
 4. To perform the appearance and clear image according to the written description;
 5. To make a third of two things.
 6. Make a drawing of the elements of the planned cutting of things.
 7. Make models of things from different materials according to the drawing.
 8. Break down the assembly drawing of the assembly unit into details.
- Above is an exercise method that develops spatial imagination. The types of training are inextricably linked with each other, and they are theoretical enough for students requires knowledge and practical skills and competence.

If the types of training are analyzed from a methodological point of view, they are It corresponds to the principle "from simple to complex". That is why we are in our business in depth some types of training methods for the development of spatial imagination we found the study methodically correct. Because students are drawing science. Studying topics related to planned projection drawing in the program perform these types of tasks in the process.

CONCLUSION

It is related to the formation and expansion of students' spatial imagination skill development is the most important component of graphics activity. None What science cannot develop spatial imagination and spatial hypothesis like drawing. The issues used in teaching practice are related to students' thinking activities it was determined to have an effect. Therefore, the desire of students to work creatively, development of spatial imagination, formation of conscious activity in the science of drawing is of great importance.

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